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Examination of the Opinions of the Parents Attending the Safe Internet and Computer Using Course on Applied Education*

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Abstract

Individuals may encounter many negativities due to the misuse of computers and the Internet. Children suffer the most from these negativities. This situation necessitates parents who always protect and stand by their children, to become knowledgeable about the safe use of computers and the Internet. In this study, we examined the opinions of the parents who participated in the safe Internet and computer use training for the parents. The participants of the study were 14 parents of students studying in the 5th and 6th grades in a state secondary school in Bartın. The data of the research were obtained using a semi-structured interview form and a personal information form including demographic characteristics. Qualitative method was used in the research and content analysis was used to analyze the data. In the research findings, the views of parents on safe computer and safe Internet use were examined. It is seen that the general purpose of the parents participating in the training organized on safe Internet and computer use is to improve themselves. When the aims of parents' participation in education are examined; there are reasons such as obtaining information about safe Internet use and completing their deficiencies, learning to use a computer, helping their children and adapting to technology. At the end of the training, the parents stated that they learned about password security, mobile security, the points to be considered in sharing information (such as sharing personal information), harmful software, the use of anti-viruses and the benefits of safe Internet use at the end of the training.

Keywords: Safe Internet and Computer Use, Information Security, Education of Parents, Lifelong Learning

1. Introduction

Today, both the scope of information and the developments in information and communication technologies (ICT) are changing rapidly and spreading in a short time. This change has had many positive contributions (Kara, 2011). However, besides the benefits that ICT has added to our lives, there are also disadvantages (Baaij, 2012; Chusavitina & Zerkina, 2016). Some human-induced problems may be encountered due to the inability of individuals to use ICT correctly (Arachchilage & Love, 2014; Shillair et al., 2015). While it is critical for

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individuals to reach the right information quickly and on time with the effect of the Internet, the elements that may threaten the information security are gradually entering our lives. The weakest link in ensuring information security is the human factor. The human factor plays a key role in ensuring an adequate level of information security (Mart, 2012). In cases where information security is compromised, loss of privacy, cyber threats and attacks are just some problems that may arise. In addition to the fact that attacks can come from malicious people in electronic environments, there are threats called social engineering that can come from our friends and people we know (Canbek & Sağiroğlu, 2006). Because of these problems, individuals suffer material and moral loss (Karaoğlu, Yılmaz, Yılmaz, & Sezer, 2014). Additionally, it brings many problems arising from the frequent use of computers and the Internet (Cengizhan, 2005). The widespread use of the Internet and mobile phones among students indicates that students communicate in cyber environments, and the communication established in these environments naturally led to the emergence of a new type of bullying called cyberbullying (Özdemir & Akar, 2011; Walvare & Heirman, 2010). Additionally, since the threats encountered increase in terms of both number and variety, ensuring the security of the information carried in mobile electronic environments comes to the fore (Bulut & Sağiroğlu, 2009). The use and protection of passwords in personal computers, social networks, e-mails or in all electronic media is also of vital importance in preventing information security risks.

According to Bilen, Ercan and Gülmez (2014), personal information, picture, video, content and profile sharing, etc. With the easy use of social networks that emerged for these purposes, users have attracted considerable attention, and both the number of these applications and the number of their users have increased, and their spread has accelerated. Social networks have now become one of the basic communication tools of individuals of all ages. All children, including primary school students, use social networks for various purposes such as communicating with their friends, playing games, and communicating with their teachers (Yorgancı, 2018). However, social networks can also have some disadvantages. Identity imitations can be made on social networks, as well as fake accounts can be opened on behalf of users. Additionally, added photos or videos can be used in other accounts for different purposes without permission (Yıldırım & Varol, 2013). Additionally, the reasons for security vulnerabilities in social networks can be expressed as non-compliance with privacy principles, the fact that users do not know how to control it, and users make themselves targets in this environment by sharing their personal information (Yavanoğlu, Sağiroğlu, & Çolak, 2012). For this reason, it is necessary to take some security measures to be protected from the negativities that may occur in social networks.

The Internet, which is an important technological development today, enables individuals to obtain the information they want in a short time, to communicate and to do many things in a short time. Additionally, the number of sites that can cause children to be adversely affected is increasing day by day. It is the duty of families to protect their children from the effects of these negative websites on the Internet.

Families must inform children about the safe use of ICT, democratically, for children to use the Internet correctly, to raise awareness of the dangers waiting for them in the Internet environment (Ayas & Horzum, 2013). Because when children face any problem, they cannot find a solution on their own and may need help. Here, they should first be able to apply to their closest parents and get information. However, when parents see themselves as technologically disadvantaged compared with their children, they cannot help their children (Smith, 2007). When the use of the Internet started to become widespread in our country, parents initially welcomed the Internet connection at home, as they thought the Internet was an interesting tool that offered new educational opportunities for their children. However, afterward, most parents realize that their children do not use the Internet for homework or research; in contrast, they realized that they spent time playing digital games, instant messaging, chatting with strangers (Yalçın, 2006). Today, childhood and adolescence spent completely away from technology cannot be imagined, and childhood spent with technology at any time may have developmental drawbacks (Akbulut, 2013). Considering this situation, it is not the right approach to ban the Internet, which is an important part of our lives, for our children due to the dangers in its structure, like any technology, and to deprive them of the possibilities of this technology. According to Kaya and Tuna (2010), the children of families who do not spend enough time with their children regardless of their education level, cannot guide their children in the safe use of ICT and do not have sufficient knowledge about these issues, are likely to spend more time with these technologies and perform undesirable behavior. Therefore, it is critical to educate parents on this issue. As a family, the first step to protect our children from the dangers of the Internet is to learn to use this technology at a basic level (Tercan, Sakarya, & Çoklar, 2012). In this respect, it is critical for parents to have sufficient information to provide correct information

to their children and to protect their children from risks (Karaođlan Yılmaz & Çavuş Ezin, 2017). The attitudes of the parents toward technology and the attitudes taken by the parents toward the technological developments directly affect the children (Odabaşı, 2005). Because the attitudes and behavior of parents have an important place in the formation of children's attitudes. The family environment in which the child is born and the characteristics it has played an important role in determining the development of the child (Kenar, 2012). Within the scope of the European On-Line Children Research Project (EU Kids Online II, 2010) realized with the participation of 25 European countries and supported by the European Commission, interviews were conducted with children aged 9–16 across Turkey and their parents, and children's Internet use and Internet risks were examined. Because of the EU Kids study is among the suggested that parents should be educated about Internet safety so that parents can use the Internet as a solution proposal, although they think that they have enough knowledge about Internet safety, but they do not have enough knowledge and skills. From this viewpoint, to use ICT, which we come across at every stage of our lives and make our work easier, the parents, who are right next to our children and are a model for them, should receive the necessary training and help their children.

It may not be possible to handle every situation encountered on the Internet. For this purpose, internet literacy skills should be at a certain level (Çelen, Çelik, & Seferođlu, 2011). According to Canbek and Sađirođlu (2007), if a parent must know where their child is outside the house alone and with whom, they should also be controlled at the computer and on the Internet, and families should have enough knowledge about the subject to guide their children.

Akkoyunlu and Tuđrul (2002) in their study aimed to determine the effect of preschool children's interactions with various technological devices at home on their computer literacy stated that children are with technological tools from an early age, and that parents' approaches affect children. Additionally, he states that the strong models presented by the parents and the conscious guidance affect all stages of the child's development positively, and that the conscious guidance of the parents is critical to expand the impact of technology positively and to eliminate the possible problems that may be caused by its uncontrolled use. Here, since it is impossible for all individuals to adapt to development and change only with the knowledge learned during school periods, it is possible for the person to constantly renew and develop himself only through lifelong learning. In modern society and education system, the skills to use ICT have become a basic requirement for lifelong learning (Yılmaz & Karaođlan Yılmaz, 2018). Besides lifelong learning, schools and universities; it can be done at work, at home, or anywhere, without any restrictions in terms of age, gender, socio-economic status and education level (Ministry of National Education [MEB], 2009). According to Miser (2002), in today's world where information and skills are constantly changing, everyone should renew and develop themselves by using adult education services. In particular, he stated that what is expected from adult education is to adapt individuals to the developing technology. From this perspective, the proximity of adults to technology is even more important. In this direction, considering the studies in the literature, it is seen that parents do not have enough information to guide their children about safe ICT use and information security and to raise awareness. The education of parents becomes necessary. This study is important in terms of providing the parents with education to be conscious individuals and thus having the knowledge to inform their children against the threats that may arise in front of the Internet and computer.

1.1. Purpose of the research

In the research, parents were given safe computer and Internet usage training and their opinions were examined because of this training. With this study, it is aimed that parents become life-long learners by ensuring that they have the knowledge to inform their children about the threats that may arise in front of the Internet and computers. When the studies in the literature are examined, it is seen that children face various negativities, but families cannot help their children because they do not have enough information on this issue, and it is thought to raise awareness for parents as suggestions. For this reason, this study is important in terms of both contributing to adult education and helping to eliminate the negativities that our children may encounter by providing safe computer and Internet usage training to parents in the lifelong learning process.

2. Method

2.1. Model of the Research

This research is a qualitative study to determine the opinions of the parents after the safe Internet and computer use training given to the parents. Qualitative research is research that uses qualitative data collection methods such as observation, interviews, and document analysis and reveals perceptions and events in a natural environment in a realistic and holistic way. (Yıldırım & Simsek, 2016). In this study, a case study, one of the qualitative research designs, was used. The purpose of most case studies is not to observe the research group and find generalized conclusions; to understand the distinctive features of the research group is to reveal the attitudes and behavior against an event by systematically explaining them (Özden & Durdu, 2016).

2.2. Working Group

The participants of the research; consisted of the parents of the students studying in the 5th and 6th grades in a public secondary school in the province of Bartın in Turkey in the fall semester of the 2017–2018 academic year. Since the compulsory information technologies and software courses are included in the curriculum in the 5th and 6th grades, the parents of these students were included in the study group. 14 volunteer parents participated in the study.

2.3. Data Collection Tool

The data of this research; personal information form and semi-structured interview form, which was finalized by obtaining expert opinion. In the personal information form, questions are prepared to determine the demographic characteristics of the parents, such as gender, age, occupation, marital status, educational status. However, in the semi-structured interview form, there are questions in which the parents will express their personal opinions about education organized.

2.4. Data Collection and Analysis

Personal information form and semi-structured interview form, which are data collection tools, are available in printed form. After the training was given, the parents' views on the training on "Safe Internet and computer use" were applied to 12 parents via audio recording and to 2 parents who did not accept the audio recording on paper. In the analysis of the data obtained through open-ended questions, the content analysis technique was used as the researcher would reveal the codes. Content analysis increases the intelligibility of the research phenomena by coding the data and bringing them together under certain themes (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). The research findings were based as the theme based on the semi-structured interview form questions and presented by creating sub-themes from the answers given by the participants to the interview questions. Sentences that were thought to be used as one-to-one quotations were determined and included as one-to-one quotations in the findings section when deemed necessary. Additionally, the frequency of the sub-themes was calculated and tabulated in frequency. The frequency values given in the study show the frequency of repetition of sub-themes, not the number of people. The data obtained in the study were recorded by the researcher, and then by a second encoder for the reliability of the study.

Miles and Huberman's (1994) reliability formula: Concordance rate = Number of coding codes that were adapted/Number of codes that were or could not be matched. A 70% agreement was considered acceptable. This gives coding reliability. Inter-coder reliability was found to be 93.03%.

2.5. Organization and Content of the Training Given

The training given to parents on safe Internet and computer use is given below under the main headings:

1. Information Security

- Malware
- Password Security
- Security in Social Networks
- Social Engineering
- Network Security
- Mobile Security

2. Why Is Safe Computer Use Important?
3. Let's Recognize the Risks Children May Encounter on the Internet.
4. Cyberbullying
5. Precautions and Solutions to be Taken for Safe Use as Parents

3. Findings

The findings and comments obtained from the research are presented below, respectively.

3.1. Findings on Demographic Characteristics

Coding was done to present the data obtained from the parents without revealing their identities and not to cause confusion. For this purpose, codes were given as P1 in the order in which the data were entered, and as “P2,” “P3,” “P4” ... “P14” respectively.

Table 3.1: Demographic characteristics of the parents participating in the study

Gender	f	%
Female	12	85.7
Male	2	14.3
Level of Education	f	%
Primary School	5	35.7
Secondary School	4	28.6
High School	5	35.7
Bachelor	-	-
Graduate School	-	-
Age	f	%
30–34	7	50
35–39	3	14.3
40–44	2	7.1
45 ve üstü	2	7.1
Professions	f	%
Homemaker	10	71.4
Self-Employment	2	14.3
Operator	1	7.1
Retired	1	7.1
Total	14	%100

As shown in Table 3.1, female parents participating in the research constitute 85.7% (f=12) of the participants, and male parents constitute 14.3% (f=2). The educational status of the parents was 5 primary school, 4 secondary school and the remaining 5 high school graduates; it is seen that the number of parents who graduated from primary, secondary and high school is close to each other.

Looking at the age distribution, it is seen that 50% of the parents are between the ages of 30–34. It is seen that the number of parents participating decreases as the age increases. When the table is examined, parents who grow up in the age of technology and who are younger are more interested in education for the use of ICT. It could be seen that most of the participants were homemakers. It can be seen that the other parents were (f=2) self-employed, (f=1) retired and (f=1) operators.

Table 3.2: Distribution of the parents participating in the study according to their possession of ICT tools

Availability of ICT Tools	f	%
Smartphone	14	100
Desktop	7	50.0
Tablet PC	5	35.7
Laptop	2	14.3
Do not own any ICT tools	-	-
Availability of Regular Internet Access	f	%
Yes	14	100
No	0	0
Average Daily Internet Usage Times	f	%
0-1 hours	8	57.1
1-4 hours	5	35.7
4-7 hours	0	-
7 h or more	1	7.1
Do you use social network? (For example, Facebook ...)	f	%
Yes	11	78.6
No	3	21.4
Do you use any anti-virus programs?	f	%
Yes	9	64.3
No	5	35.7
What is the meaning of lifelong learning? Explain it	f	%
Learning will continue from birth to death	12	85.71
Improve yourself throughout the life	1	7.14
Get information continually	1	7.14
Total	14	100

When the parents participating in the study had ICT tools, it was seen that everyone has a smartphone. The presence of smartphones for every parent can show that individuals have kept up with the digital age. It seems that everyone has regular Internet access. It was determined that 78.6% (f=11) of the parents used social networks and

21.4% (f=3) did not use social networks. Considering the use of antivirus, it is seen that 64.3% (f=9) of the parents use antivirus program and 35.7% (f= 5) do not.

It can be seen that most of the parents participating in the study could explain the concept of lifelong learning. Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P3: "There are many things to learn as long as our lives go on. I continue to learn. I will continue."

P6: "It is never too late to learn. We need information at every age, and it is more efficient when it is done knowingly."

P9: "I think a mother should learn everything she can learn in life and should be a model for her children."

3.2. Findings Related to Research Questions

The findings and comments obtained for the research are presented as follows.

The answers to the question of the factors or factors that enable the parents who participated in the training organized on safe Internet and computer use to participate in this training (Self-development, contributing to professional development, socializing, closeness of the course, to adapt to technological developments, etc.) are shown in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3: Elements that enable you to participate in the training organized on safe Internet and computer use

Sub-themes	f	%
For improving myself	11	28.20
For helping my child	7	17.94
For adapting new technologic improvements	6	15.38
To socialize	6	15.38
For getting information and fixing the shortcomings	3	7.69
Contribute to professional development	2	5.12
To help the environment and friends	2	5.12
As it is useful	1	2.56
As it is close to the course	1	2.56
Total	39	100%

When Table 3.3 is examined, it is seen that 28.20% (f=11) of the answers given by the parents who participated in the training organized in safe internet and computer use for the factors that enable them to participate in the training is self-improvement. Here, it can be said that most parents are lifelong learners. It is seen that 17.94% (f=7) of the answers were to help our children, 15.38% (f=6) to keep up with technological developments and 15.38% (f=6) to socialize.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below:

P8: "I think I will say many elements. I especially wanted to be useful to my child, I developed myself, I socialized, I wanted to adapt to other technologies."

P14: "It was self-development, keeping up with technological developments, helping our children."

P3: "for my child to socialize and improve myself"

The answers given to the question stating what kind of benefits the education received by the parents are in terms of ensuring information security are shown in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Benefits of the training given to ensure information security

Benefits of the training given to ensure information security	f	%
Password security (Password usage etc.)	9	19.56
Mobile security	7	15.21
Things to consider when sharing information (Personal information should not be shared etc.)	6	13.04
Backing up information	5	10.86
Usage of social networks and security	5	10.86
Usage of safe internet	3	6.52
Malware and usage of antivirus	3	6.52
Correct use of flash memories	2	4.34
Every downloaded file should not be used	2	4.34
Usage of public wi-fi	2	4.34
Protection against risks on the Internet, such as cyberbullying	2	4.34
Total	46	100%

When Table 3.4 is examined, 19.56% (f=9) of the parents' answers to the benefits of the training in ensuring information security are password security, 15.21% (f=7) mobile security, 13.04% (f=6) information sharing things to be considered (such as sharing personal information). Additionally, (f=3) malicious software, use of antivirus and (f=3) safe Internet use were mentioned as the benefits of education. Parents stated that they benefited from this training in terms of password security, mobile security and information sharing.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P5: "I think it is useful in providing information security, in mobile security, in smartphones, in password security, when passwords are used everywhere."

P8: "Thanks to the training I received, I learned that information security is beneficial for many things. Most importantly, I was not using a password. I learned to use a password. I learned how to ensure mobile security. I learned how to use passwords. I was using a very simple password in some places. And I learned that it was bad and in a safer way."

P10: "we should not share our information with anyone, that we should back up the information. I also realized that mobile security issues are even more important in social networks."

Table 3.5: Benefits of safe Internet and computer use training

Benefits of safe Internet and computer use training	f	%
This enabled us to help our children with lessons	5	13.88
To be able to recognize the risks that our children and we will encounter on the Internet and precautions to be taken.	5	13.88
Ensuring information security	4	11.11
Safe computer usage	3	8.33
Ability to follow new technological developments	3	8.33
Learning malware	2	5.55
Safe Internet usage	2	5.55

Improve yourself	2	5.55
Ability to protect our personal computer	2	5.55
Recognizing cyberbullying	1	2.77
Socializing	1	2.77
Checking whether sites are trustworthy or not	1	2.77
Enabling us to obtain information	1	2.77
Rely on yourself	1	2.77
Enabling us to control our children's internet usage	1	2.77
Ensuring safe social media usage	1	2.77
Saving time using the internet (placing an order, finding recipe etc.)	1	2.77
Total	36	100%

When Table 3.5 is examined, it is seen that 13.88% (f=5) of the answers given by the parents about the benefits of education provided enable us to help our children in the lessons, and 13.88% (f=5) provided them to realize the risks that our children and we will encounter in the Internet and the precautions to be taken. 11.11% (f=4) of the answers stated that they provide information security, 8.3% (f=3) stated that they can follow technological developments closely and 8.3% (f=3) stated that they use secure computers.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P2: "I think it is beneficial for both myself and my child. For my child's lessons, for Facebook, for social media."

P8: "I was casually accessing the Internet, at least now I learned how and in what way, it was very useful for not harming myself and my computer."

P12: "Information security, keeping up with technology, what should be considered when using a computer, how do we protect our children."

Table 3.6: Parents' ability to contribute to their children's safe Internet and computer use because of this training

Because of this training, how will you contribute to your children's safe Internet and computer use?	f	%
Enabling and observing our children's internet usage under control	5	17.24
Providing our children with the opportunity to help with what we have learned in case of need	5	17.24
Ensuring them that they prefer age-appropriate and reliable sites	4	13.79
Protecting our children against the risks they face on the internet	3	10.34
Usage of social media	3	10.34
Using a secure password	2	5.17
Providing information on malware	2	5.17
Helping to cope with cyberbullying	2	5.17
Understanding the importance of using a computer	1	2.58
To have knowledge with reliable education	1	2.58

Being able to teach password creation criteria	1	2.58
Total	29	100%

When Table 3.6 is examined, it is seen that 17.24% (f=5) of the answers given by the parents on how they can contribute to safe Internet and computer use for their children because of this training is that they can provide the opportunity to control and monitor their children's Internet use, and (f=5) to help their children with what they learn when needed. Additionally, 13.79% (f=4) of the answers expressed their contribution to their children as making them prefer age-appropriate and reliable sites.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P3: *“Children were playing games, I didn't know which games were what, which sites they were on. Now I've learned a little about social media. I'll do my best.”*

P8: *“I can teach or learn to use the Internet well with my child, I can follow him and at least with my child I can discuss which sites are safe, how much and how.”*

P13: *“I learned how to protect the computer from viruses, what to pay attention to when setting a password, how to deal with cyberbullying.”*

Table 3.7: Suggestions for negative behavior solutions on the Internet observed by parents after education

Explain how to follow the path toward negative behaviors.	f	%
Controlling where my child goes	4	23.52
Time restrictions on tablet and phone use	3	17.64
Enabling access to trusted sites (starting with http)	2	11.76
Telling to be careful	2	11.76
Trying to talk when closed in, telling	1	5.88
Ensuring the safe use of the internet	1	5.88
Limiting the shares to the familiar ones from the settings on social media	1	5.88
Warning about adware	1	5.88
Ensuring that he/she must tell me about the bad situations to be encountered.	1	5.88
Saying not to share personal information	1	5.88
Total	17	100%

When Table 3.7 is examined, 23.52% (f=4) of the answers given by the parents for the solution suggestions for the negative behavior observed in their children on the Internet after education, were to act in a controlled manner about where their child enters, and 17.64% (f=3) to limit the time in the use of tablets and phones. 11.76% (f=2) stated that they should access reliable sites, and 11.76% (f=2) stated that they should be careful.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P1: *“We do both the game and homework together anyway. We will do it together in a more controlled way.”*

P8: *“I can at least follow these ways for my child to play games or enter sites that start with http at the beginning and use the Internet more properly. Now I realize that we must go in together.”*

P10: "I would say that he should prefer reliable sites, that he may face bad situations, and that he should not be friends with everyone on social networks."

The areas where parents need information security training in terms of adults are shown in Table 4. 40.

Table 3.8: After receiving this training, the areas of information security where education is needed for adults

After receiving this training, the areas of information security where education is needed for adults	f	%
Social network security	13	27.08
Safe Internet use	11	22.91
Using anti-virus	8	16.66
Smartphone use	8	16.66
Mobile security	3	6.24
In all areas of information security	2	4.16
E-mail security	2	4.16
Password security	1	2.08
Total	48	100%

When Table 3.8 is examined, 27.08% (f=13) of the answers given by the parents to the areas where information security needs training in terms of adults after receiving this training are social network security, 22.91% (f=11) safe Internet use, 16.66% (f=8) smartphone usage, 16.66% (f=8) anti-virus usage.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P5: "After this training, it can be social network security, safe Internet use, anti-virus."

P11: "Social network security and smartphone use after training.

P9: "After receiving this training, you can send your own information about using social networks, it can be damaged, of course, anti-virus is also important, if you learn to use safe Internet, risks are actually avoided, and a smartphone is also a necessity."

Table 3.9: Solution suggestions for parents when they encounter social engineering after education

If you encountered such a situation after this training, what solutions would you suggest?	f	%
I will report to the police	9	33.33
I don't share my personal information, password, account number, etc.	6	22.22
I immediately close the site or the phone	3	22.22
I will report to the web notification address	3	11.11
I will be careful and never trust such people.	3	11.11
I block the malicious person	1	3.70
If my password is compromised, I will change it	1	3.70
If I come across a social network, I report it with a complaint.	1	3.70

Total	27	100%
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When Table 3.9 is examined, 33.33% (f=9) of the answers given by the parents for the solution suggestions they will bring when they encounter social engineering after the training, 22.22% (f=6) report my personal information, password, account number, etc. not sharing, 11.11% (f=3) shutting down the site and phone immediately, 11.11% (f=3) I will change my password if it is captured, and other 11.11% (f=3) is to be careful and not to trust such people.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P8: "I never give my personal information to people who ask me for my personal information, and if I can't deal with it, I can definitely reach the web notification address."

P10: "Do not share my personal information, password, account number, etc. about myself if I come across it. I will report it to the police immediately."

P12: "Definitely do not provide personal information, I complain about social networks. I'll either call the police or call the hotline if its online."

Table 3.10: The benefits of the training to the parents in creating and using passwords on their personal computers.

How did this training raise awareness about creating and using passwords on your personal computer?	f	%
I understand that it is important to set my own personal password and not to share it.	8	25
I used to prefer easy passwords (such as date of birth), now I prefer hard passwords	7	21.87
Setting a hard password according to security criteria prevents us from being harmed by bad people.	7	25%
By opening a guest account for anyone who uses the computer other than us, I will not share my own password.	5	15.62
In the past, my computer used to open directly, now it opens with a password.	5	15.62
Total	32	100%

When Table 3.10 is examined, it is seen that 25% (f=8) of the answers given to the parents about creating and using passwords on their personal computers understand that it is important to set my own personal password and not to share it, and 21.87% (f=7) prefer an easy password beforehand. (for example, date of birth), that they now prefer difficult passwords, 21.87% (f=7) stated that determining a difficult password according to security criteria prevents harm from bad people.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P5: "Awareness has been created on the computer, an account is created for everyone to use, a separate user account for the guest, for the family, for the child, so that he does not learn the incoming password, he enters from the guest account."

P7: "We didn't know how to set a password, now we set a password, it was useful for us, it was beneficial for our children, we know it, we don't share it with anyone."

P13: "What is private to me should be strong because only I can access it, it should not be told to anyone, it should not be an easy password."

Table 3.11: The effects of this training on the safe use of social networks

Can you explain in detail what effect this training has had on the safe use of social networks?	f	%
I act safer by sharing my social networks with my friends only.	10	29.41

I am setting up a security privacy setting.	9	26.4
I do not edit and share my Personal Password that I use on social networks.	5	14.7
I use social networks more carefully because using social networks unconsciously can cause negative situations.	4	11.76
I can block those who have bad behaviors, such as threats, cyberbullying	2	5.8
I have restrictions on my profile	2	5.8
We can take control of our children with what we learn on social networks	2	5.8
Total	34	100%

When Table 3.11 is examined, 29.41% (f=10) of the answers given by the parents to the effects of this training on the safe use of social networks, they acted more safely by sharing on social networks only with their friends, 26.47% (f=9) made security-privacy settings, % 14.7 (f=5) stated that they did not organize and share their personal passwords that they used in social networks. Additionally, (f=4), there are also answers stating that using social networks without knowing can cause negative situations, so they will use it more carefully.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P2: "Need to set the security privacy settings. I shouldn't give my password to anyone."

P6: "I create my own secure password on social networks. Then, I can set a limit on my profile. I take such measures to prevent anyone from accessing my information."

P8: "I learned what I can do for my child, how important the password is, and since I learned security settings on the computer in this training, I should not share my important information with other people, make privacy settings, and not share many things with other people."

When Table 4.49, 100% of the parents stated that the education they received created awareness about protecting their computers or other electronic devices from harmful software.

Table 4.51 shows what the parents will do after the training to protect their computers or other electronic devices from harmful software.

Table 3.12: Situations by parents will adopt after training on protecting their computers or other electronic devices from harmful software

Situations by parents will adopt after training on protecting their computers or other electronic devices from harmful software	f	%
It is necessary to use an antivirus program on PCs or mobile devices.	12	39.99
When installing a new program on the computer, I must scan it with an antivirus program.	4	13.33
Flash etc. devices should not be opened without scanning them with an antivirus program.	4	13.33
I learned that I should clean my computer periodically by scanning it with an antivirus program.	4	13.33
If we save our information and make a backup, we will protect our information.	3	9.99
I determined that one of the software systems that harms the computer is viruses	2	6.66
I learned that the firewall also protects against malware.	1	3.33

Total **30** **100%**

When Table 3.12 is examined, 40% (f=12) of the answers given by the parents about what they can do after the training to protect their computers or other electronic devices from malicious software is that it is necessary to use an antivirus program on PCs or mobile devices, 13.33% (f=4) when installing a new program on the computer, it is necessary to scan with an anti-virus program, 13.33% (f=4) say flash etc. on the computer. 13.33% (f=4) stated that devices should not be opened without scanning them with an anti-virus program, and that it is necessary to clean their computers by scanning them periodically with an anti-virus program.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P2: "Must scan when installing a program on the computer."

P8: "I learned that there are many kinds of viruses on the computer, I knew them by hearsay before the training. Now, with this training, I have learned what to do, use an antivirus program, and clean my computer properly."

P10: "I didn't know we had to scan the files we downloaded. We should pay attention to the use of anti-viruses and firewalls to be protected from malicious software.

Table 4.53 shows the awareness that education brought to the parents about paying attention to modem password security.

Table 3.13: Awareness gained by the training about giving importance to the password security of your modem

After this training, how did you raise awareness about giving importance to the password security of your modem that you use at home?	f	%
I learned that the modem password should not be shared outside family members.	10	30.30
The first password provided after the modem is purchased must be changed.	6	18.18
It is necessary to determine the password is hard to find according to security criteria.	6	18.18
We should not allow the shared use of the modem.	6	18.18
The password should be changed periodically for security.	2	6.6
It is more appropriate to give names to the modem that cannot be identified as ours.	2	6.6
Now, I know not to use known passwords.	1	3.3
Total	33	100%

When Table 3.13 is examined, 30.30% (f=10) of the answers given by the parents to the importance of paying attention to the password security of the modems they use at home after this training, stated that the modem password should not be shared outside the family members, and 18.18% (f=6) stated that after the modem is purchased. the first password given must be changed, 18.18% (f=6) stated that it is necessary to determine the password as difficult according to security criteria, and 18.8% (f=6) stated that we should not allow shared use of the modem.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P2: "Do not put my date of birth because others know, things to be known should not be used, I do not share them, Sir."

P4: "Do not give or share my modem password with anyone. It would be difficult."

P10: "Modem password is critical. We must edit the password according to certain security criteria. We must change it periodically. And we need to be mindful of shared use."

Table 3.14: Awareness raised by this training to protect parents from the risks that their children may encounter on the Internet

Are there any situations that you did not do before the training, but would do after the training, about protecting your children from the risks that they may encounter on the Internet?	f	%
When using the Internet, I take care to use it under control with my child or in the same room.	6	20
I inform my child about the risks he will face.	6	20
We should be very careful about cyberbullying.	3	10
After the training, I paid attention to my child's posts on social networks and to his friends.	3	10
Children should be told that personal information should not be shared.	2	6.66
I can prevent the risks by reducing the usage time of our children by putting a password on my personal computer.	2	6.66
Now my child will not be able to act according to his own mind because he knows that I also gain knowledge.	2	6.66
If my child is uneasy or distressed when he/she spends time on the internet, I talk to him/her.	1	3.33
I'm thinking of using a filtering program to protect it from harmful content by filtering it to safe sites.	1	3.33
After the training, I pay attention to whether the games my child plays are appropriate for his/her age.	1	3.33
We can reduce these risks by protecting our computers from malicious software.	1	3.33
Total	30	100

When Table 3.14 is examined, 20% (f=6) of the answers given by the parents to the awareness that the education they receive about protecting their children from the risks they may encounter on the Internet is that they take care to use the Internet with their child or in the same room under control, 20% (f=6).) stated that they will inform their child about the risks he/she will face. Additionally, 10% (f=3) state that they should be careful about cyberbullying, and 10% (f=3) state that they pay attention to their children's posts on social networks and friends.

Some of the parents' opinions are given below.

P11: "According to age groups, I can use the computer in a common area, so I can keep it under control, I can tell what to use and where."

P10: "Internet is both beneficial and harmful. After education, for example, there is a change in the behavior of the child who is exposed to cyberbullying. I pay attention to this. Who do you make friends on social networks? Who sees what you share? These are important. I will check if the games he will play are suitable for his age group."

P12: "We should be more careful. Especially when creating passwords and surfing social networks. We should only share our personal information and the photos on social networks with familiar people. Passwords that are difficult to find and mixed should be determined. This is the first time I've heard of cyberbullying. Great attention must be given. Also, you must scan the computer and back it up."

4. Discussion

There are various conveniences that information and communication technologies provide to our lives. Computers and the Internet open the doors of the world to learn, have fun and communicate. However, if the necessary knowledge is not obtained, the harms are also encountered. For this purpose, considering that education begins in the family, safe computer and Internet use by parents, who are role models for their children, becomes even more important. Thus, it is expected that their children will be lifelong learners by protecting them from the harms they may encounter. Considering the situation of explaining the concept of lifelong learning, all parents were aware of the concept of lifelong learning, and most of them stated that learning would continue from the cradle to the grave. The most important reason why parents turn to this education is that they want to improve themselves. According to this result, thanks to the parents who are aware of the necessity of lifelong learning, it is expected that their children will be individuals who are self-confident and open to learning. Ayaz (2016), in his study examining teachers' lifelong learning tendencies, states that those with a high level of lifelong learning are more willing to participate in courses, seminars, and symposiums related to personal and professional development, and that these studies are an important factor in the lifelong learning process. The findings of this study are similar to the research of Ayaz (2016). It is seen that the most important factor enabling parents to participate in the training organized on safe internet and computer use is self-improvement. Thus, they support the purpose of lifelong learning. All the parents who participated in the study stated that they achieved their purpose of participation. They stated that they achieved their goals by gaining knowledge through this education, not completing their deficiencies, helping their children, learning to use computers and following technological developments. In the study of Oskay and Yurttas (2013), when the evaluation of the benefit of the parents participating in the research on the use of the Internet by their children, most parents were of the opinion that it is beneficial in terms of research and information, in terms of homework and lessons. Accordingly, the aims of parents in using the Internet for themselves and their children are similar.

They stated that they benefited especially in password security (using passwords, determining passwords according to security criteria) and mobile security at the point of providing information security in education. They also stated that they benefited from the things to be considered in sharing information. Cagiltay et al. (2011), it is stated that 46% of the children participating in the study did not know the rules for protecting their personal information and shared their personal information such as the date of birth with everyone. It is thought that this study will contribute to information security by transferring parents who have incomplete information about the things to be considered in sharing information with this education.

According to the findings, because of this training, providing the parents with the opportunity to control their children's Internet use, to observe them, and to help their children with what they have learned if they need it is the contributions of this education for their children. Additionally, it is one of the other contributions expressed that it enables them to prefer reliable sites suitable for their age. In the study of Oskay and Yurttas (2013), the most important reason for the families participating in the study was to provide an Internet connection to their homes; most of the respondents stated that it is for the benefit of their children. Here, it can be said that the primary purpose of parents is always to help their children.

Akbulut (2013) study supports the recommendations of the parents to follow the course of their children's undesirable behavior on the Internet after receiving the training, to be controlled by the parents about where my child enters, to limit the time in the use of tablets and phones, to access reliable sites (starting with http). Demirel, Yörük, and Özkan (2012) found in their study that when the rules that parents impose on their children's use of the Internet are examined, they prohibit access to certain websites and limit the time spent on the Internet. Additionally, Holloway, Green, and Brady (2013) stated that parents should limit their children's screen time, which supports the statement given by parents as a solution to negative behavior. In the Tercan, Sakarya, and Çoklar (2012) study, it is similar to the measures taken by their families regarding the use of the Internet as expressed by the students.

According to the results of the research, the parents stated that after receiving this training, the greatest need for information security is social network security, safe Internet use, antivirus and smartphone use. According to Avinç (2017), the fact that children cannot properly evaluate the situations they encounter in social networks due to their inability to distinguish between real information and interpretation on the Internet also causes families to worry. When the answers given by the teachers about information security are analyzed in the study of

Canoğulları (2021), in which the teachers' information security awareness levels are analyzed, it is seen that the teachers have moderate knowledge about information security. This shows the necessity for adults to receive training on information security.

According to the results of the research, it was stated that if the parents encountered an incident related to social engineering, they would first notify the police as a solution proposal. Additionally, personal information, passwords, account number, etc. with suspects. They said they would not share.

According to the results of the research, all the parents stated that the training provided raises awareness about creating passwords, they understand that it is important to set their own personal password and not to share it, they used to prefer easy passwords (such as date of birth), but now they prefer difficult passwords, according to security criteria. They stated that setting a password prevents harm from bad people.

In the study of Karaoğlan Yılmaz and Çavuş Ezin (2017), the parents' efforts to create complex passwords that cannot be guessed easily and to create passwords consisting of letters, numbers and special characters to ensure password security support the answers given by the parents after the training. In the study of Yılmaz et al. (2017), which examined high school students' awareness of secure computer and Internet use, the fact that most of the students could not create reliable and difficult to obtain passwords for password security is similar to the result encountered by the parents before the education. According to the results of the research, when the effects of the majority of the parents on the safe use of social networks were examined, the majority of them stated that they acted more securely by sharing with only my friends on social networks, and they made security-privacy settings. Akgün and Topal (2015), in their study with university students, show similarities with the opinions of parents after the education in that students make arrangements for privacy and security settings in social networks regarding social network security and attach importance to the protection of personal information. In Yorgancı's (2018) study examining parental attitudes towards children's use of social media, it was found that some parents did not know the concept of social media fully and because of this situation, they could not act consciously enough about their children's use of social media. Parents, who stated that social networks have benefits, showed contradictory attitudes about the harms and precautions to be taken in the answers given in the continuation. This situation supports the views of the parents before education. For this reason, it is thought that the education that will be given to the parents will contribute greatly to their children.

They stated that education provided the situations that parents would adopt to protect their computers or other electronic devices from harmful software. In Tekerek and Tekerek's (2013) research, it is similar to the low awareness of students on issues such as checking for malware, protecting documents, personal computer security, using firewalls and filtering software. After the training, most of the parents stated that it is necessary to use an antivirus program on computers or mobile devices and stated that they increased their awareness on this issue. Additionally, in the study of Karaoğlan Yılmaz, Yılmaz, and Sezer (2014), the statements of using an antivirus program and updating the antivirus program also support the statements of the parents, when looking at the precautions taken by university students to protect themselves from harmful programs.

After this training, all the parents raised awareness about giving importance to the password security of the modems they use at home. Most parents stated that the modem password should not be shared with family members, to the awareness gained by education (Karaoğlan Yılmaz, Yılmaz, & Sezer, 2014). Additionally, it is among the other awareness that the parents stated that the first password of the modem should be changed, that the passwords to be determined should be difficult to determine according to the security criteria and that the modem should not be used jointly. In the study of Karaoğlan Yılmaz and Çavuş Ezin (2017), the parents stated that they created strong passwords that are difficult to guess and did not share them with anyone, to ensure the security of the Internet connection.

The education provided is about protecting their children from the risks they may encounter on the internet. They stated that they will inform their children about the risks and that they take care to use the Internet with their children or in the same room under control. In Oğur (2016)'s study, when parents' reactions to students' activities on the Internet are examined, it is similar to the post-education behavior of parents that they allow activities such as playing games, watching videos and listening to music on the Internet, with the knowledge of or under the supervision of their parents. Additionally, most of the students stated that their mothers did not know how to use

the Internet. This shows that no matter how conscious parents are about the Internet, they need to be educated about it. Training organized for this purpose is a critical issue.

5. Suggestions

Considering that development continues throughout life, everyone should have sufficient knowledge and skills. The fact that technology is indispensable at every aspect of our lives has made information security and the safe use of computers and the Internet even more important. Children born in the age of technology are the ones who are most exposed to the risks in the internet environment. For this reason, safe Internet use training was given to parents to create conscious families.

Suggestions are listed below:

- When we look at the studies in the literature, it is seen that even the educated adults cannot make up for the deficiencies in information security. For this reason, it may be recommended to provide training on safe Internet and computer use to adults working in different institutions.
- In the literature, studies have been conducted to determine the views of parents on the conscious use of the Internet. However, within the scope of lifelong learning adult education to address their deficiencies, parents can be socialized and self-development by organizing regular training with school-family cooperation.
- The children of the parents participating in the study are studying in the 5th and 6th grades. Students take the information technologies and software course, which is a compulsory course, at school. By asking children's opinions on safe Internet and computer use, both data diversity and curricular evaluations can be made.
- In this study, the research was examined in depth using the qualitative method, it can be supported with quantitative findings.
- In the study, the parents of the students expressed the areas they need in terms of information security as social network security and safe Internet use. For this purpose, social network security can be preferred as a separate study subject in education.
- Since the parents participating in the study had transportation problems, a time limit was applied, but since the parents also found education useful and wanted to participate in similar training, new studies could be conducted by increasing the number of parents, and by choosing the parents of the children studying in the 7th and 8th grades, a difference could be made.
- The content of the training to be organized can be decided by conducting a survey on safe Internet and computer use to the students by looking at their deficiencies. Thus, adult education can be supported in the lifelong learning process.
- The subject of risks in the Internet environment can be preferred as a new study topic since parents are anxious about the risks their children may face in the Internet environment, and because they participate in the training for this purpose.

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